

A Survey on Pneumatic Wall-Climbing Robots for Inspection

Angelica Brusell, George Andrikopoulos and George Nikolakopoulos

Abstract—The aim of this article is to present a survey on inspection applications of Pneumatic Wall-Climbing Robots (PWCR). In general, a PWCR utilizes negative pressure as its adhesion method, through mainly suction cups or negative pressure thrust-based mechanisms. Their main advantage being their ability to climb non-ferromagnetic surfaces, such as glass and composite materials, in comparison with climbing robots based on magnetic adhesion methods. A growing application area is the utilization of PWCRs for inspection purposes for accelerating the otherwise time consuming procedures of manual inspection, while offering the important advantage of protecting human workers from hazardous and/or unreachable environments. This article will summarize the key enabling inspection applications of PWCRs in the following areas: a) Construction, b) Industrial Infrastructures, as well as c) Aircraft applications.

I. INTRODUCTION

The research area of Wall-Climbing robots (WCR) has steadily gained interest over the years as a promising approach to remote inspection and maintenance of big and hard to reach spaces. The development of reliable WCRs with Inspection capabilities would significantly cut maintenance costs in areas where manual inspection times are high and the worker security might be compromised. The improved visual feedback and measurement possibilities could improve inspection quality as well as speed up the overall process. A WCR could also operate in environments that are hazardous to humans, such as chemical storage tanks or structures at great heights, hence the continued research on Wall-Climbing Robots for inspection purposes is a key to improve industrial security [1], [2].

A number of different adhesion and locomotion methods have been applied in various combinations to solve the problems of the Pneumatic Wall-Climbing Robots (PWCRs) motion, while remaining attached onto sloping surfaces. The most common adhesion methods are: a) magnetic, b) pneumatic, c) gripping, and d) Biometric. The ferromagnetic requirements of climbing materials for the utilization of a magnetic adhesion method limits their general use for inspection, whereas gripping adhesion methods suffers from their reliability on surrounding geometry, like ledges and rails. The main advantage of PWCRs is their ability to climb onto a wider range of materials, such as composites, walls and tanks, ferromagnetic as well as non-ferromagnetic. This survey will only focus on the existing pneumatic adhesion methods for inspection robots and their applications.

This work has received funding from the European Union's H2020 Framework Programme under the call FET-OPEN, grant agreement No 665238.

A. Brusell, G. Andrikopoulos and G. Nikolakopoulos are with the Control Engineering Group, Luleå University of Technology, SE-97189 Luleå, Sweden. Corresponding Author's E-mail: geonik@ltu.se

The two main pneumatic methods for achieving adhesion are: a) suction cups [3], and b) negative pressure-thrust [4]. Suction Cups (SCs) (Fig 1.2) are most commonly used due to the simplicity of their design and operation principle. One major drawback is the constant need for attachment/detachment from the surface for achieving locomotion, thus limiting their movement speed. They also suffer from vacuum leakage over time, as well as a sensitivity to cracks and abnormalities in the surface material, which results in a loss of adhesion force. This means that SC-based robots require a step-wise locomotion method, namely legged and translational movement, which enables their attachment/detachment on and from the target surface. On the other hand, Negative Pressure-Thrust (NPT) adhesion (Fig 1.1) has the advantage of supporting a constant negative pressure that increases the mobility of the robot. NPTs commonly apply wheel-driven locomotion to achieve continuous movement across the surface. The major drawback of NPTs is also their advantage, meaning the fact that they don't require contact with the target surface. This can protect sensitive surfaces from damage during locomotion, but creates the need of using high-power motors to achieve and maintain the required constant negative pressure.

The aim and the contribution of this article is to provide a survey on inspection applications of PWCRs, which will be categorized as: a) adhesion method, and b) locomotion method, as well as their intended industrial inspection application areas. Due to the promise of this technology such a survey will provide a bibliographical basis for further

Fig. 1. Two types of Pneumatic Wall-Climbing Robots: (1.1) CROMSCI [5] using Negative Pressure-Thrust adhesion and Wheel-Driven Locomotion, and (1.2) W-Climbot [6] using vacuum suction cups and Legged Locomotion.

studies and investigations in the field of Pneumatic Inspection Robotics.

The rest of this article is structured as follows. Section II covers the fundamental adhesion and locomotion methods for PWCRs. In Section III, the most significant applications of PWCRs for inspection purposes are presented by categorization in respective scientific fields. Finally, the conclusions are provided in Section IV.

II. FUNDAMENTAL PRINCIPLES OF PNEUMATIC WALL-CLIMBING ROBOTS

PWCRs can be categorized via two major operational methods: a) adhesion and b) locomotion. These methods exist in a number of combinations, the most important of which will be highlighted in this Section.

A. Adhesion mechanism

1) *Suction cups*: A suction cup is an elastic and flexible object capable of creating a partial vacuum, i.e. negative pressure, to adhere to nonporous surfaces, capable of providing a large weight-to-force ratio [7]. SCs are divided into two main categories, depending on the generation of the vacuum adhesion: a) passive: and b) active.

In passive suction, the partial vacuum is achieved via physical pressure of the cap against the desired surface. When the physical pressure is ceased, the elastic material tends to return to its original curved shape. The duration of the suction effect depends on the time it takes for the air to leak back into the cavity between the cup and the surface.

On the other hand, in active SCs the partial vacuum is achieved via the use of an external vacuum generator. Air is constantly sucked from the adhesion cavity, causing a stronger adhesion to the desired surface. This advantage made active SCs the governing choice for use in adhesion mechanisms.

Surface abnormalities and cracks decrease the operating efficiency of SCs, as they cause leakage in the vacuum seal, and hence loss of adhesion force. A work around to this problem is to equip the PWCRs with multiple suction cups so that if a cup suffers from vacuum leakage the rest can compensate.

Fig. 2. SC-based configurations: (2.1) Translational high payload WCR [8], (2.2) MRWALLSPECT II [9] one suction cup per leg.

One suction cup at each leg is typically used when the size requirements are small. [10], [11], [12], [13], [14].

Three to five suction cups are typically used when the WCR uses leg-based locomotion to ensure adhesion despite crack and abnormalities [6], [15], [16], [17], [18]. More than five suction cups are typically used in big two legged robots, which need to be able to carry high payloads, or medium sized translational movement PWCRs [9], [19], [20], [21], [22]. In order to ensure sufficient adhesion of larger translational PWCRs with high payloads, the needed SCs can reach impressively high numbers e.g. 50 [8]. In addition, SCs have also been used in legged PWCRs for extra adhesion force [14], [16].

2) *Negative Pressure-Thrust*: Negative Pressure-Thrust (NPT) is an adhesion method that has grown fast in WCR-related applications. The adhesion mechanism functions as a SC without the requirement of a vacuum seal against the surface, instead a high speed rotor is used to continuously remove the air between the wall and bottom plate of the robot [4], [7], [23], [24], [25].

In this approach, successful aerodynamic attraction to the target surface is achieved via the utilization of a vacuum impeller-based mechanism, which is connected to a vacuum motor (Fig. 3.1). The high speed rotation of the impeller causes the air flow to form an aerodynamical swirl effect that causes the pressure to drop, an effect that intensifies closer to the center of the impeller (Fig. 3.2). In this way, the generated negative pressure leads to an aerodynamic attraction to the target surface. It has to be noted that for the maximum available attraction, the impeller should be selected with the proper blade profile and dimensions, while the appropriate motor type should be utilized as to be able to produce high-speed rotations.

The advantages of this method is that no contact with the target surface is required, which provides an inherent non-destructive testing (NDT) characteristic. The use of external pneumatic equipment (e.g. vortex generator) is avoided, and thus the overall concept results in a more compact and autonomous design. On the down side, the utilization of a vacuum motor and additional equipment (sensors, motor controller etc.) is essential, which increases the complexity of the setup the overall weight, dimensions and the design complexity. Furthermore, in this case, the suction area is limited to the center part of the impeller mechanism, which increases the difficulty of supporting large payloads due to the constant air leakage from the outer impeller sections.

Fig. 3. (3.1) Vacuum Impeller-based concept for aerodynamic attraction, (3.2) Distribution map of negative pressure on the bottom view of the impeller mechanism (darker colors correspond to larger values of absolute negative pressure and stronger attraction).

Larger attraction forces can be generated with the use of more powerful motors or larger impeller dimensions, which increases the overall power consumption, dimensions, weight and drag torque of the vortex robot, thus also affecting the restrictions posed on the maximum payload.

B. Locomotion mechanism

1) *Leg-based Locomotion:* A common method for locomotion in SC-based PWCRs is the legged motion as depicted in Figure 4. This type of motion offers the step-wise operation that is required by the SCs, as well as the ability of implementing multiple Degrees of Freedom (DOF) and obstacle avoidance capabilities. Disadvantages of this locomotion strategy are the low speeds and the need for advanced control systems that tend to be highly complicated.

Fig. 4. Two types of leg-based PWCRs: (4.1) RAMR1 biped WCR [10], and (4.2) MRWALLSPECT III [16] quadruped robot.

One approach to simplify the control problem of such PWCRs is the incorporation of a biped design [6], [10], [15], [19], [26], which limits the complexity of the system, but also the available DOFs and overall speed of the system.

The use of a quadruped design [11], [16], [14], increases system complexity but provides more adhesion points to the surface, thus making it less sensitive to possible adhesion loss of one suction cup.

2) *Translational Locomotion:* Translational locomotion refers to a strategy based on a sequential motion pattern. This type of movement is however simpler from a control perspective, but suffers from size and speed issues.

PWCRs utilizing translational locomotion typically have two frames that can move in relation to the other. Each frame has a number of suction cups for surface adhesion, and in alternating steps each frame attaches to the target surface as the other frame moves into its new position. This motion strategy is inspired by the sequential motion pattern of a caterpillar [8], [9], [12], [17], [18], [20], [21], [22], [27], [28], [29].

3) *Wheel-driven motion:* Wheel-driven locomotion is only applied in the cases of NPT-based PWCRs as their continuous adhesion force application allows for their continuous motion, although they suffer from poor obstacle avoidance and slipping if not controlled properly.

A number of different implementations of wheel-driven locomotion has been presented in related bibliography, such

Fig. 5. Wheel-driven NPT PWCRs: (5.1) CROMSCI three omni-directional wheeled robot [5], and (5.2) Alicia 2 two wheel-based PWCR [30].

as omni-directional wheels [5], [31], [32], two independently controlled wheels [30], [33], belt driven [34], and the more conventional four wheel configuration [35], [36], [37], [38].

III. APPLICATIONS OF PNEUMATIC WALL-CLIMBING ROBOTS FOR INSPECTION PURPOSES

A. Inspection of Construction Applications

One of the most common inspection application of PWCRs has been the examination of infrastructures, e.g. buildings and bridges, for the detection of cracks and structure irregularities, which when performed manually tends to become an extremely time consuming and hazardous task. Furthermore, this application area has been popular due to the PWCRs wide compatibility of target surfaces, as buildings are typically constructed of non-ferromagnetic materials.

The bridge climbing robot, depicted in Fig. 6.1 [36], was designed to inspect cracks in bridge walls and big support pillars. In this concept and through high definition images, taken with an on-board camera, and transmitted in real time through a tele-communication link to the image processing computer, the state and over-all health of the structure can be analyzed. Alicia1 (Fig. 6.2), Alicia2 (Fig. 5.2) and Alicia3 (Fig. 6.9) [30] were designed for NDT of large concrete walls, such as highway bridges and dams, and to detects cracks via the use of ultrasonic heads. The PWCR presented in Fig. 6.3 [35] was developed to perform visual inspection of cracks in concrete structures using a camera. The camera feedback from the robot was image processed at ground level. ROBIN (Fig 6.4) [15] was designed to carry cameras and relevant sensor equipment for inspection of large infrastructure, such as bridges, buildings, aircraft and ships. The double-cavity climbing robot (Fig. 6.5) [39], [40] was developed with glass-wall inspection in mind. Ninja-I and II (Fig. 6.6) [11], Robug II (Fig. 6.7) [14] and ROMA2 (Fig. 6.8) [19] were designed for inspection of buildings and other infrastructures, each one specialized on scanning different parts and materials. Wall inspection has also been a popular application executed by similar PWCRs found in related bibliography (Fig. 6.10) [29], [37]. Furthermore, CROMSCI (Fig. 1.1) [5] was designed for non-destructive test (NDT) of large concrete walls, e.g. dams and bridge

Fig. 6. Inspection of Construction Applications: (6.1) Bridge inspector [36], (6.2) Alicia1 [30], (6.3) Robotic inspector of concrete cracks [35], (6.4) ROBIN [15], (6.5) Double-cavity climbing robot [39], [40], (6.6) NINJA-I, II [11], (6.7) Robug IIs [14], (6.8) ROMA2 [19], (6.9) Alicia3 [30], and (6.10) Robotic inspector of glass-walls [29].

pylons, while being equipped with an impulse radar to detect holes inside the concrete and a high-resolution camera to detect cracks of 0.2mm width. Finally, the W-Climbot (Fig. 1.2) [6] and SIRIUSc [28] were designed for general inspection of construction and infrastructure.

B. Inspection of Industrial Infrastructures

The inspection of a tank's interior has always been considered a difficult task, since it could contain toxic substances or could be located in areas difficult to reach manually e.g. under ground. To address this issue, a number of PWCRs have been proposed in order to perform such inspection routines.

Specifically, VIRIV (Fig. 7.1) [34] was developed for weld and critical spot inspection inside storage tanks through visual inspection. MRWALLSPECT II (Fig. 2.2) [9] and MRWALLSPECT III (Fig. 4.2) [16] were both designed for ultrasonic NDT inspection of the outside of oil or gas tanks. ROBICEN I, II and III, depicted in Fig. 7.2 were developed for nuclear plant contamination monitoring and inspection of steam and water leaks in hazardous environments [12], [17], [27]. SURFY (Fig. 7.4) [20] was developed to inspect and measure corrosion levels in e.g. industrial tanks or other metallic materials, whereas the robots displayed in (Fig. 7.3) [31] and (Fig. 7.5) [26] were designed for general structural inspection of hazardous environments, e.g. nuclear plants and toxic storage tanks.

C. Aircraft Inspection

PWCRs have also been introduced in aviation, for the inspection of aircrafts' outer hall. The Multifunction Auto-

mated Crawling System MACS (Fig. 8.1) [21] was developed to carry out inspections of large aircrafts via ultrasonic sensors, in order to detect cracks and other abnormalities in the aircraft's exterior surface. Similarly the NDT robot displayed in Fig. 8.2. [8] was developed at the London South Bank University for the inspection of aircraft wings and fuselage. Due to its flexible structural implementation and active vacuum suction cups it was able to carry a payload up to 18 kg. Fig. 8.3 and 8.4 [22] displays Lufthansa's aircraft inspection robot MORFI, which was equipped with NDT sensory equipment in order to asses the health of the aircrafts fuselage.

D. PWCRs for General Inspection Purposes

Among PWCRs, introduced for generic inspection purposes, the RAMR1 (Fig. 4.1) was introduced in [10] for the inspection and assessment of hazardous environments, such as biological hazards and hostile situations inside buildings or confined spaces.

The Micro Aerial Vehicle (MAV) (Fig. (9.1) [32] is a hybrid development with both UAV and Wall-Climbing features for inspection of wind turbines. By the usage of four rotors the robot can fly to the blades of the wind turbine where it attaches itself and performs the surface inspections. The Sizewell 'A' Duct Inspection Equipment (SADIE) (Fig. 9.2) [41] was developed to perform weld inspections in tight and hazardous environments that are inaccessible to humans via the use of ultrasonic scanning for the analysis of the quality and status of the welds.

Another PWCR found in related literature is Bigfoot [42],

Fig. 7. Inspection of Industrial Infrastructures: (7.1) VIRIV [34], (7.2) ROBICEN III [17], (7.3) General inspection robot [31], (7.4) SURFY [20], and (7.5) Small Climbing Robot for the Intelligent Inspection of Nuclear Power Plants [26].

Fig. 10. Generic Inspection PWCRs: (10.1) [38], (10.1) WALKMAN-I [18], (10.3) Fuzzy bot [13], (10.4) [33].

Fig. 8. Aircraft inspection PWCRs: (8.1) MACS [21], (8.2) NDT PWCR [8], (8.3) and (8.4) MORFI [22]

which was designed for risk assessment of large infrastructure, mainly with regards to seismic risk, while keeping a low-cost profile in order to enable its commercial availability.

Fig. 9. Other inspection applications: (9.1) MAV [32], (9.2) SADIE [41].

In addition, a number of PWCRs have also been developed following the concept of inspection as the target application, although they were not equipped with the necessary equipment.

The PWCR developed at Harbin Institute of Technology (Fig 10.1) [38] was designed as a platform for inspection equipment for construction applications as well as rescuing missions. The WALKMAN-I (Fig 10.3) [18] was a small, lightweight PWCR and its inspection advantage lied in its ability to reach tight inaccessible spaces where manual

inspection is hard or even impossible. Similarly the two robots (Fig. 10.2 and 10.4) [13], [33] were developed as general platforms for inspection purposes.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this article a survey on Pneumatic Wall-Climbing Robots (PWCRs) for Inspection was presented. The fundamental principles of Adhesion and Locomotion for PWCRs have been discussed and was mainly focused on the inspection applications of PWCRs. These applications were divided into four categories, a) Construction, b) Industrial Infrastructures, c) Aircraft and Other applications, with a detailed overview of the most important PWCRs that were identified in related bibliography.

From the review of the inspection applications of PWCRs it has been revealed an increasing trend of robots for infrastructural inspection. This growing interest is reflecting the promising results of the existing technological developments of PWCRs, while the continuous research on this subject will help in maintaining a high inspection standards in service and thus preserving the infrastructure health at high levels.

Given the large number of PWCRs that have been developed and specialized in infrastructure inspection, this survey also revealed the potential of researching and developing PWCRs for the challenging application of aircraft inspection, via the use of modern design techniques and advanced

control structures in order to overcome the challenges of the aircraft's curved composite surfaces. Overall, the results of the survey can be summarized in the following Table I.

Adhesion	Locomotion	Pros	Cons
Suction Cups	Leg-based	Good obstacle avoidance	Slow
Suction Cups	Translational	Easy control	Slow
NPT	Wheel-based	Continuous motion	Complex control

TABLE I

PROS AND CONS OF ADHESION AND LOCOMOTION MECHANISMS.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Armada, P. G. de Santos, M. A. Jimenez, and M. Prieto. Application of CLAWAR Machines. *Int. J. Rob. Res.*, 22(3-4):251–264, 2003.
- [2] Baeksuk Chu, Kyungmo Jung, Chang Soo Han, and Daehie Hong. A survey of climbing robots: Locomotion and adhesion. *Int. J. Precis. Eng. Manuf.*, 11(4):633–647, 2010.
- [3] Yu Yoshida and Shugen Ma. Design of a Wall-Climbing Robot with Passive Suction Cups. *2010 IEEE Int. Conf. Robot. Biomimetics*, pages 1513–1518, 2010.
- [4] Jun Li. Wall climbing robot based on negative pressure-thrust suction method. *2008 IEEE Int. Conf. Mechatronics Autom.*, pages 604–609, 2008.
- [5] C. Hillenbrand, D. Schmidt, and K. Berns. CROMSCI: development of a climbing robot with negative pressure adhesion for inspections. *Ind. Robot An Int. J.*, 35(3):228–237, 2008.
- [6] Yisheng Guan, Haifei Zhu, Wenqiang Wu, Xuefeng Zhou, Li Jiang, Chuanwu Cai, Lianmeng Zhang, and Hong Zhang. A Modular Biped Wall-Climbing Robot With High Mobility and Manipulating Function. *IEEE/ASME Trans. Mechatronics*, 18(6):1787–1798, 2013.
- [7] Zhijian Jiang. Study on pneumatic wall climbing robot adhesion principle and suction control. *2008 IEEE Int. Conf. Robot. Biomimetics*, pages 1812–1817, 2009.
- [8] Jianzhong Shang, Tariq Sattar, Shuwu Chen, and Bryan Bridge. Design of a climbing robot for inspecting aircraft wings and fuselage. *Ind. Robot An Int. J.*, 34(6):495–502, 2007.
- [9] H.R. Choi, S.M. Ryew, T.H. Kang, J.H. Lee, and H.M. Kim. A wall climbing robot with closed link mechanism. *Proceedings. 2000 IEEE/RSJ Int. Conf. Intell. Robot. Syst. (IROS 2000)*, 18(4):2006–2011, 2000.
- [10] M. Minor, H. Dulimarta, G. Danghi, R. Mukherjee, R. Lal Tummala, and D. Aslam. Design, implementation, and evaluation of an under-actuated miniature biped climbing robot. *Proceedings. 2000 IEEE/RSJ Int. Conf. Intell. Robot. Syst. (IROS 2000)*, 3:1999–2005, 2000.
- [11] S Hirose, A Nagakubo, and R Toyama. Machine that can walk and climb on floors, walls and ceilings. *Fifth Int. Conf. Adv. Robot. Robot. Unstructured Environ.*, 1:753–758, 1991.
- [12] L. Briones, P. Bustamante, and M.a. Serna. Wall-climbing robot for inspection in nuclear power plants. *Proc. 1994 IEEE Int. Conf. Robot. Autom.*, pages 1409–1414, 1994.
- [13] J. Xiao, N. Xi, R.L. Tummala, and R. Mukherjee. Fuzzy Controller for Wall-Climbing Microrobots. *IEEE Trans. Fuzzy Syst.*, 12(4):466–480, 2004.
- [14] Bing L. Luk, David S. Cooke, Stuart Galt, Arthur a. Collie, and Sheng Chen. Intelligent legged climbing service robot for remote maintenance applications in hazardous environments. *Rob. Autom. Syst.*, 53(2):142–152, 2005.
- [15] RT Pack. A rubber-tuator-based structure-climbing inspection robot. *IEEE International Conf. Robot. Autom.*, (April):1869–1874, 1997.
- [16] Quadruped Walking and Climbing Robot. Quadruped Walking and Climbing Robot. (October), 2003.
- [17] J. Savall, A. Avello, and L. Briones. Two compact robots for remote inspection of hazardous areas in nuclear power plants. *Proc. 1999 IEEE Int. Conf. Robot. Autom.*, pages 1993–1998, 1999.
- [18] Hong-quan Gao, Zhi-an Zhang, Yan-qing Lai, Jie Li, and Ye-xiang. Liu. Development and control of flexible pneumatic wall-climbing robot. *J. Cent. South Univ. Technol. (Engl. Ed.)*, 15(6):830–834, 2008.
- [19] C. Balaguer, A. Gimenez, and CM. Abderrahim. ROMA robots for inspection of steel based infrastructures. *Ind. Robot An Int. J.*, 29(3):246–251, 2002.
- [20] Guido La Rosa, Michele Messina, Giovanni Muscato, and R Sinatra. A low-cost lightweight climbing robot for the inspection of vertical surfaces. *Mechatronics*, 12(1):71–96, 2002.
- [21] Paul G. Backes, Yoseph Bar-Cohen, and Benjamin Joffe. The Multifunctional Automated Crawling System (MACS). *Int. Conf. Robot. Autom.*, (April):335–340, 1997.
- [22] Lufthansa Technik. Morfi. 2014.
- [23] D Schmidt, K Berns, and J Ohr. Analysis of sliding suction cups for negative pressure adhesion of a robot climbing on concrete walls. *Proceeding 15th Int. Conf. Climbing Walk. Robot.*, 6:813–820, 2012.
- [24] Qian Zhi-yuan, Zhao Yan-zheng, Fu Zhuang, and Wang Y. Fluid Model of Sliding Suction Cup of Wall-climbing Robots. *Int. J. Adv. Robot. Syst.*, 3(3):1, 2006.
- [25] A Fallah, M Rezasoltani, A Riasi, and H Moradi. Numerical Analysis of a Non-Contact Surface Adhesion System based on Vortex Cup for Wall Climbing Robots. *RSI/ISM Int. Conf. Robot. Mechatronics*, pages 368–373, 2013.
- [26] Da Guan, Lei Yan, Yibo Yang, and Wenfu Xu. A Small Climbing Robot for the Intelligent Inspection of Nuclear Power Plants. *4th IEEE Int. Conf. Inf. Sci. Technol.*, 2014.
- [27] Avello A. Briones L. Serna, M. A. and P Bustamante. ROBICEN: A Pneumatic Climbing Robot for Inspection of Pipes and Tanks. *Lecture Notes in Control and Information Sciences, Vol. 232*, pages 325–334, 1998.
- [28] N Elkmann, Torsten Felsch, Mario Sack, J. Saenz, and J. Hortig. Innovative service robot systems for facade cleaning of difficult-to-access areas. *IEEE/RSJ Int. Conf. Intell. Robot. Syst.*, 1(October):756–762, 2002.
- [29] Dong Sun, Jian Zhu, Chiming Lai, and S.K. Tso. A visual sensing application to a climbing cleaning robot on the glass surface. *Mechatronics*, 14(10):1089–1104, 2004.
- [30] Domenico Longo and Giovanni Muscato. The Alicia Climbing Robot. *Robot. Autom. Mag. IEEE*, Volume:13(March):42–50, 2006.
- [31] Wang Yan Wang Yan, Liu Shuliang Liu Shuliang, Xu Dianguo Xu Dianguo, Zhao Yanzheng Zhao Yanzheng, Shao Hao Shao Hao, and Gao Xueshan Gao Xueshan. Development and application of wall-climbing robots. *Proc. 1999 IEEE Int. Conf. Robot. Autom.*, 2(May):1207–1212, 1999.
- [32] Sungwook Jung, Jae-uk Shin, Wancheol Myeong, and Hyun Myung. Mechanism and system design of MAV (Micro Aerial Vehicle)-type wall-climbing robot for inspection of wind blades and non-flat surfaces. *15th Int. Conf. Control. Autom. Syst.*, pages 1757–1761, 2015.
- [33] Jizhong Xiao Jizhong Xiao, A. Sadegh, M. Elliott, A. Calle, A. Persad, and Ho Ming Chiu Ho Ming Chiu. Design of Mobile Robots with Wall Climbing Capability. *Proceedings, 2005 IEEE/ASME Int. Conf. Adv. Intell. Mechatronics.*, pages 24–28, 2005.
- [34] Mohamed G Alkalla, Mohamed A Fanni, and Abdel-fatah Mohamed. Versatile Climbing Robot for Vessels Inspection. *Int. Conf. Control. Autom. Robot.*, pages 18–23, 2015.
- [35] Praveen Sekhar and R.S. Bhooshan. Duct Fan Based Wall Climbing Robot for Concrete Surface Crack Inspection. *IEEE India Conf.*, 2014.
- [36] O L X Qmxvw and H G X Fq. Adhesion-adaptive control of a novel bridge-climbing robot. *IEEE Int. Conf. Cyber Technol. Autom. Control Intell. Syst.*, pages 102–107, 2013.
- [37] Akira Nishi. A Wall Climbing Robot Using Propulsive Force of Propeller, 1991.
- [38] Yili Fu, Zhihai Li, Hejin Yang, and Shuguo Wang. Development of a wall climbing robot with wheel-leg hybrid locomotion mechanism. *2007 IEEE Int. Conf. Robot. Biomimetics, ROBIO*, pages 1876–1881, 2008.
- [39] Ran Liang, Rong Liu, Chunwei Yang, and Ke Wang. Design, Modeling and Analysis of a Climbing Robot Used for Inspection of Glass Curtain Walls. *IEEE Int. Conf. Robot. BiomimeticsI*, (December), 2013.
- [40] Ke Wang, Rong Liu, and Yuan Qu. Development of a Double-Cavity Climbing Robot for On-Site Inspection of Glass-Curtain-Walls. *IEEE Int. Conf. Inf. Autom.*, (August):1183–1188, 2013.
- [41] Tim White, Neal Hewer, Bing L LUK, and Jeff Hazel. The design and operational performance of a climbing robot used for weld inspection in hazardous environments. *IEEE Int. Conf. Control Appl.*, (September):451–455, 1998.
- [42] T. White and D. Cooke. Robosense/Robotic delivery of sensors for seismic risk assessment. *Proc. International Conference on Climbing and Walking Robots, CLAWAR, Madrid, Spain*, (August):847–852, 2000.